

MEDICAL SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF USING SIMULATORS AND VARIOUS MODELS TO TRAIN RESIDENTS IN THE SPECIALTY OF NEUROSURGERY

Kaunbekova Sh.

*Department of Surgical Diseases, Karaganda Medical University
Kazakhstan,
Multidisciplinary Hospital named after Professor Kh.Zh. Makazhanov
Karaganda, Kazakhstan*

Abstract

Neurosurgery is a rapidly evolving speciality that requires the physician to constantly evolve with the times and use a variety of modern equipment. Residency graduates must be proficient in a variety of surgical techniques to provide expert care to patients.

The article reflects the analysis of problems of neurosurgical residents training and ways of their solution. It is suggested to introduce the experience of training of foreign colleagues into the system of training of our residents, based on the analysed literature data, described systems of training of residents of different countries, their use of simulators and various models to practice practical skills.

Keywords: neurosurgery residents, simulation training, use of 3 D models.

Introduction: Training of residents in the speciality of neurosurgery (adult, paediatric) is carried out in accordance with the state obligatory standards on the levels of education in the field of health care. The initial stage of postgraduate continuing education in neurosurgery in the Republic of Kazakhstan is currently the residency in adult and paediatric neurosurgery, which is designed for four years (280 credits) [1,2,3]

The entire training plan is conducted in accordance with the educational programme, which includes the objectives, results and content of training, the organisation of the educational process, ways and methods of their implementation, criteria for evaluating the results of training.

The residency programme is aimed at mastering such types of professional activities as: therapeutic, preventive, diagnostic and rehabilitative. In order to provide specialised care to neurosurgical patients, it is necessary to have fundamental theoretical training and to possess practical skills at a high professional level.

Neurosurgery in recent years has become one of the most advanced high-tech surgical specialities and training of specialists in this field requires an individual approach and much more training time. There is an obvious need to increase and include in the course programme the development of various manual skills [3, 4, 5]

Materials and methods:

In Karaganda State University in the educational programme on the specialty of neurosurgery modules and disciplines are distributed as follows: the first year of training is the discipline of the basics of neurosurgery (33 credits), which includes the study of neuroanatomy, propaedeutic of neurosurgical diseases, clinical-diagnostic and instrumental methods of research in neurosurgery, as well as included disciplines such as neurophysiology and neuropathomorphology, general surgery.

Further disciplines by nosologies (pediatric neurosurgery, craniocerebral trauma, spinal cord trauma,

vascular pathologies of the brain and spinal cord, degenerative dystrophic diseases of the spine, tumors of the central nervous system) are distributed by years.

The educational process is distributed as follows 30% practical skills, independent work of the resident under the guidance of the teacher -60%, independent work of the resident -10%.

Residents spend most of their training time in neurosurgical departments (adult and pediatric). Under the supervision of clinical mentors, residents learn basic neurosurgical skills in the first year, then participate in surgery as an assistant. In the third and fourth years of training, under the supervision of clinical preceptors, residents perform a variety of access surgeries on the brain, spinal cord, and peripheral nervous system. In addition, residents engage in research activities on a selected topic during their training under the supervision of their mentors. They write articles and participate in competitions of young scientists [1,2].

Analyzing the training systems of different countries by level of development, for example, in the Russian Federation to obtain a certificate of a neurosurgeon undergo a two-year clinical residency. According to the authors, 2 years of training time in residency is considered not sufficient for mastering all neurosurgical skills for further work. It is suggested to include different simulation models in the training process [4,5,6,7]

The U.S. training for a neurosurgeon is 7 years of training. Residents learn their practical skills in simulation laboratories where they can learn various surgical techniques for the brain, spinal cord and peripheral nervous system depending on the intervention required, under the supervision of mentors. One year of training is devoted to research work. In the seventh year of training, the resident performs surgical interventions independently.

A 14-item survey on the role of simulation in neurosurgical resident education was conducted in the United States. 99 directors of educational programs of neurosurgery in the USA participated in the survey. The questionnaire asked about the role of the model and

simulation, the clinical skills of residents that could influence the trainee's future work as a physician.

According to the survey results, 72% responded that the use of simulation improves patient outcomes, 74% responded that it complements basic treatment well, and 25% responded that it can replace traditional treatment. 45% of leaders believe that resident work on simulation models will prepare residents for difficult or rare cases in treating patients in the future. Many supervisors indicated that they would be willing to allocate more time and money to purchase a simulation. Among simulation models, preference was given to cadaver, less to virtual simulations and physical models [8, 9].

In their work, the authors also note the usefulness of a simulator with 3D printing of silicone for training residents in vascular pathologies, for example, cerebral aneurysms, where residents could practice clipping techniques. Various anatomically similar models of the ventricular system of the brain have been modeled from cast hydrogel using 3D printing for residents to perform ventriculostomy surgery for various occlusive hydrocephalus [10, 11, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17].

Stimulators were also used to practice the practical skills of residents by combining 3D printing and special effects for minimally invasive surgery in neurosurgery. The authors, with the help of modeling engineers and special effects specialists, created a head model of a 14-year-old child with hydrocephalus, taking into account all anatomical features, on which residents and fellows practiced the skill of performing an endoscopic ventriculostomy of the third ventricle. Skill performance was assessed by experienced senior residents using a 14-item Likert questionnaire and the Objective Structured Assessment of Technical Skills (OSATS) scale. OSATS = Objective Structured Assessment of Technical Skills [12, 19, 20, 21].

Conclusions:

The ways to solve the existing problems can be the active introduction of internships in neurosurgical clinics and simulation laboratories of foreign countries in the educational program of residents. Having analyzed the system of training residents in the specialty of neurosurgery in different countries, we can say that the inclusion of simulators, special effects and 3D modeling in the training program for the acquisition of surgical skills will allow residents to encounter frequently encountered pathologies, increase not only in the knowledge of anatomy, but also to make progress in surgical skills, to gain self-confidence, which will certainly have a positive impact on the quality of the intervention.

References

1. Order of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Kazakhstan from July 4, 2022 № КР ДСМ-63. Registered with the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Kazakhstan on July 5, 2022, No. 28716. On approval of state mandatory standards for levels of education in the field of health care <https://adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/V2200028716>.
2. On making amendments and additions to the order of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Kazakhstan "On approval of the list of medical specialties of residency programs" from May 25, 2021 № КР

ДСМ - 43 and "On approval of model curricula for medical and pharmaceutical specialties" from January 9, 2023 № 4.

<https://adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/V2300033629>

3. Kuzgibekova A.B., Abeuova B.A., Kenzhebayeva G.A., Yeryomicheva G.G., Babenko M.B., Zhumakanova K.S Modern aspects of training residents on speciality of pediatrics International Journal of Applied and Fundamental Research №3, 2017 <https://s.applied-research.ru/pdf/2017/3-2/11442.pdf>

4. Yarikov A.V, Kalinkin A.A, Pavlinov S.E, Garipov I.I, Perlmutter O.A, Fraerman A.P, Tsybusov S.N, Mukhin A.S, Ignatieva O.I, Simonov A.E Neurosurgeon training in Russia: modern problems and ways of their solution [in Russian] Bulletin of Science and Practice Volume: 9 Number: 4 Year: 2023 Pages: 349-357 <https://doi.org/10.33619/2414-2948/89/40>

5. Usachev D. Y., Konovalov A. N., Likhterman L. B., Konovalov N. A., Matuev K. B. Neurosurgeon training: current problems and modern approaches // Voprosy neurosurgery. N.N. Burdenko. 2022. T. 86. № 1. C. 5-16 <https://doi.org/10.17116/neiro2022860115>

6. Krylov V. V., Levchenko O. V., Zakondyrin D. E. Practical training of neurosurgeons in Russia. Part 1. Problems and ways of their solution // Neurosurgery. 2017. №1. C. 72-78. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/podgotovka-neyrohirurga-v-rossii-sovremennyye-problemy-i-puti-ih-preodoleniya>

7. Yakovenko I. V., Kondakov E. N., Zakondyrin D. E., Pirskeya T. N. Simulation training of basic neurosurgical skills in residency // Russian Neurosurgical Journal named after Prof. A.L. Polenov. 2014. T. 6. №4. C. 50-54. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/obuchenie-neyrohirurga-v-rossii-sovremennyye-problemy-i-puti-ih-resheniya>

8. Ganju A., Aoun S. G., Daou M. R., El Ahmadieh T. Y., Chang A., Wang L., Bendok B. R. The role of simulation in neurosurgical education: a survey of 99 United States neurosurgery program directors // World neurosurgery. 2013. V. 80. №5. P. e1-e8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wneu.2012.11.066>

9. Fallah A., Ebrahim S., Haji F., Gillis C., Girgis F., Howe K., Wallace M. C. Surgical activity of first-year Canadian neurosurgical residents // Canadian journal of neurological sciences. 2010. V. 37. №6. P. 855-860. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0317167100051568>

10. Justin R. Ryan^{1,2}, Kaith K. Almefty³, Peter Nakaji³, David H. Frakes^{1,2,4} Cerebral Aneurysm Clipping Surgery Simulation Using Patient-Specific 3D Printing and Silicone Casting <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/26805698/>

11. Ryan JR, Chen T, Nakaji P, Frakes DH, Gonzalez LF Ventriculostomy Simulation Using Patient-Specific Ventricular Anatomy, 3D Printing, and Hydrogel Casting. World Neurosurg. 2015 Nov;84(5):1333-9. doi: 10.1016/j.wneu.2015.06.016. Epub 2015 Jun 20. PMID: 26100167 <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/26100167/>

12. Weinstock P, Rehder R, Prabhu SP, Forbes PW, Roussin CJ, Cohen AR. J Creation of a novel simulator for minimally invasive neurosurgery: fusion of 3D printing and special effects. Neurosurg Pediatr. 2017 Jul;20(1):1-9. doi: 10.3171/2017.1.PEDS16568. Epub 2017 Apr 25. PMID: 28438070

13. Mashiko T, Otani K, Kawano R, Konno T, Kaneko N, Ito Y, Watanabe E. Development of three-dimensional hollow elastic model for cerebral aneurysm clipping simulation enabling rapid and low cost prototyping. *World Neurosurg.* 2015 Mar;83(3):351-61. doi: 10.1016/j.wneu.2013.10.032. Epub 2013 Oct 16. PMID: 24141000
14. Wang L, Ye X, Hao Q, Ma L, Chen X, Wang H, Zhao Y. Three-dimensional intracranial middle cerebral artery aneurysm models for aneurysm surgery and training. *Clin Neurosci.* 2018 Apr;50:77-82. doi: 10.1016/j.jocn.2018.01.074. Epub 2018 Feb 10. PMID: 29439905
15. Leal AG, Mori YT, Nohama P, de Souza MA. Three-Dimensional Hollow Elastic Models for Intracranial Aneurysm Clipping Election - A Case Study. *Annu Int Conf IEEE Eng Med Biol Soc.* 2019 Jul;2019:4137-4140. doi: 10.1109/EMBC.2019.8856514. PMID: 31946781
16. Graffeo CS, Bhandarkar AR, Carlstrom LP, Perry A, Nguyen B, Daniels DJ, Link MJ, Morris JM. That which is unseen: 3D printing for pediatric cerebrovascular education. *Childs Nerv Syst.* 2023 Sep;39(9):2449-2457. doi: 10.1007/s00381-023-05987-0. Epub 2023 Jun 5. PMID: 37272936
17. Chawla S, Devi S, Calvachi P, Gormley WB, Rueda-Esteban R. Evaluation of simulation models in neurosurgical training according to face, content, and construct validity: a systematic review. *Acta Neurochir (Wien).* 2022 Apr;164(4):947-966. doi: 10.1007/s00701-021-05003-x. Epub 2022 Feb 4. PMID: 35122126 Free PMC article. Review.
18. Bouattour Y, Sautou V, Hmede R, El Ouadhi Y, Gouot D, Chennell P, Lapusta Y, Chapelle F, Lemaire JJ. A Minireview on Brain Models Simulating Geometrical, Physical, and Biochemical Properties of the Human Brain. *Front Bioeng Biotechnol.* 2022 Mar 28;10:818201. doi: 10.3389/fbioe.2022.818201. eCollection 2022. PMID: 35419353 Free PMC article. Review.
19. Breimer GE, Bodani V, Looi T, Drake JM. Design and evaluation of a new synthetic brain simulator for endoscopic third ventriculostomy. *J Neurosurg Pediatr.* 2015 Jan;15(1):82-8. doi: 10.3171/2014.9.PEDS1447. PMID: 25360853
20. Ploch CC, Mansi CSSA, Jayamohan J, Kuhl E. Using 3D Printing to Create Personalized Brain Models for Neurosurgical Training and Preoperative Planning. *World Neurosurg.* 2016 Jun;90:668-674. doi: 10.1016/j.wneu.2016.02.081. Epub 2016 Feb 24. PMID: 26924117
20. A microcontroller-based simulation of dural venous sinus injury for neurosurgical training. Cleary DR, Siler DA, Whitney N, Selden NR. *J Neurosurg.* 2018 May;128(5):1553-1559. doi: 10.3171/2016.12.JNS162165. Epub 2017 Jun 2. PMID: 28574314